

The EOSC-Life WP4 toolbox: Update of the categorisation system (version 3)

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1. Introduction

The Horizon 2020 project EOSC-Life brings together the 13 Life Science ‘ESFRI’ research infrastructures to create an open, digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research (<https://www.eosc-life.eu/>). Sharing sensitive data is a specific challenge within EOSC-Life. For that reason, a toolbox is being developed, providing information to researchers who wish to share and/or use sensitive data in a cloud environment in general, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in particular. The sensitivity of the data may arise from its personal nature but can also be caused by Intellectual Property considerations, biohazard concerns, or the Nagoya protocol. The toolbox will not create new content, instead, it will allow researchers to find existing resources that are relevant for sharing sensitive data across all participating research infrastructures (F in FAIR). The toolbox will provide links to recommendations, procedures, and best practices, as well as to software (tools) to support data sharing and reuse. The current design document provides an outline for the anticipated toolbox, as well as its basic principles regarding content and sustainability (1).

Only resources referring directly or indirectly to **sensitive data** are included in the toolbox. The following **definition** of sensitive data is used for the project (2):

“Information that is regulated by law due to possible risk for plants, animals, individuals and/or communities and for public and private organisations. Sensitive personal data include information related to racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership and data concerning the health or sex life of an individual. These data could be identifiable and potentially cause harm through their disclosure. For local and government authorities, sensitive data are related to security (political, diplomatic, military data, biohazard concerns, etc.), environmental risks (nuclear or other sensitive installations, for example) or environmental preservation (habitats, protected fauna or flora, in particular). The sensitive data of a private body concern in particular strategic elements or elements likely to jeopardise its competitiveness.”

The toolbox will be based upon a tagging (categorisation) system, allowing consistent labelling and categorisation of resources. The first version of the tagging system, which was published in December 2020, has been defined in a separate document (3) and has been intensively tested in a pilot study (December 2020– February 2021) involving 6 research infrastructures, 12 experts and 110 resources related to sensitive data (4). As a result of the pilot study, major feedback for improvement of the categorisation system has been received and proposals for a revised set of resource tags have been made. A strong need was expressed to reduce observer variation by clearer definitions and better distinction between tags and to keep the system as simple as possible. Consequently, an updated

version of the categorisation system has been provided (April 2021, version 2, (5)). In a next step the 110 resources from the pilot study were re-tagged with the updated categorisation system version 2. This was performed between May and July 2021. Following the re-tagging exercise and the feedback received, it was felt necessary to further improve and simplify the categorisation system and to provide an updated version 3. In the present document, version 3 is described together with the changes made compared to version 2 and the updated definitions.

The re-tagged resources using version 3 will provide the initial content for the toolbox demonstrator.

2. Changes in version 3 compared to version 2

2.1 New dimension “Sensitive data type”

The category “data type” was considered too complex and created major discussion after the re-tagging exercise. Several experts strongly suggested to better define this category and to make it easier to apply. It was only possible to distinguish between “personal” and “sensitive” for the “any type of data” tag and not for the other specific data types; this was considered a serious limitation. It was therefore suggested to add an extra category “type of sensitive data” with a list of the main 4-6 types of sensitive data (e.g., personal data, environmental data, proprietary data, DURC related data, classified information). This makes the categorisation a bit more extensive but easier to apply. For that reason, “Sensitive data type” was included as **dimension 0** with 6 tags:

- Personal data
- Environmental data
- Proprietary data
- DURC data
- Classified information
- Other sensitive data

2.2 Changes for existing tagging dimensions

- **Resource type**

This dimension of the categorisation system was not changed.

- **Research field**

The tag “any research field” was added to the list.

In the re-tagging exercise, the issue was raised that there is substantial overlap between “biomedical research” and “cell biology, molecular biology and biochemistry” and it is difficult to differentiate. “Medical/health research” is differentiated in the categorisation system according to “clinical research” and “biomedical research”, the latter including basic and translational research in medicine. It may be that “cell biology, molecular biology and biochemistry” is applied in “biomedical research”. In that case both tags should be applied.

- **Data type**

“Any type of data” was included on the tags list.

Due to the introduction of a new dimension “sensitive data type”, the dimension “data type” could be considerably simplified. On the 1st level, the “data type” is structured according to “Data from living humans” and “Data not derived from living humans”. On the 2nd level, the specific data type is characterised. The list of specific data types is similar between human and non-human data with a few exceptions (routine health data, clinical research data only for human data).

- Data from living humans
 - Any type of data
 - Population level health/or socioeconomic data
 - Real world or routine health data
 - Clinical research data
 - Public health emergency data
 - Biobank and sample data
 - Data with images of humans
 - Omic and related data (from living humans)
 - Other specific data type (from living humans)

- Data not derived from living humans
 - Any type of data
 - Population level
 - Real world
 - Observational/Interventional research
 - Public health emergency data
 - Biobank and sample data
 - Data with images
 - Omic and related data (from non-living humans)
 - Other specific data type (from non-living humans)

The tag “qualitative research data” was deleted because it was not used in the pilot study and the re-tagging exercise. This data type should be covered under “other specific data type” (data from living humans). The use of the tag “biobank and sample data” was clarified in the definitions.

- **Stage in data sharing life cycle**

For some of the experts, the “data sharing life cycle” was hard to select, many resources did not clearly fall in one category. Also, the difference between “not applicable” and “whole cycle” was perceived as rather vague. In addition, the meaning of the tag “usage, scientific output and impact of data sharing” was not clear to some experts. Finally, it was argued that quite a few resources will deal with primary data registration, which cannot be selected from the list of tags.

Following the discussion, the tag “usage, scientific output and impact of data sharing” was deleted from the list of tags for two reasons: very rarely used and difficult to define. The tag “primary data registration” was included in the list. The rest of the tags was kept. The use of “not applicable” versus “whole cycle” was clarified. If a stage (or stages) in the data sharing life cycle cannot be allocated to the resource, it is “not applicable”. If the full data sharing life cycle is covered, it is “whole cycle”.

- **Geographical scope**

This dimension was kept in its present form. There was some discussion, what determines the geographic scope: the origin of the resource or the applicability of the resource? Because this was already clearly formulated in the description of the categorisation system, version 2, no changes to the definition were performed. The geographic origin of the resource's authors or its source organisation is not important – it is the **scope of the resource itself** that is relevant.

- **Specific topics**

This dimension was kept but the list of tags was considerably reduced.

“Dual Research of Concern” and “Access and benefit sharing and the Nagoya protocol” could be deleted because these tags are covered under the new dimension “sensitive data type”. “ELSI” was selected for around 50% of the resources, so it was seen as too generic. ELSI covers ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) or aspects (ELSA) of sciences. Because these aspects are already covered with “social sciences, legal or ethical research” under “research field”, this tag was deleted. “Interventional studies” were seen more as a data type or a research field. Because it was rarely used and only used by one research infrastructure (only by ECRIN, n=7, 6%), it was deleted from the dimension “specific points”.

All changes made resulted in a categorisation system version 3 with 7 dimensions and 65 tags.

EOSC-LIFE WP4 toolbox: Categorisation system (short form, version 3, final, 26 October 2021)						
0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Sensitive data type (n=6)	Resource type (n=5)	Research field (n=12)	Data type (n=18)	Stage in DS life cycle (n=6)	Geographical scope (n=5)	Specific topics (n=13)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal data ● Environmental data ● Proprietary data ● DURC data ● Classified information ● Other sensitive data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legislation and regulations ● Guidelines, recommendations and policies ● Descriptions of (best) practice ● Support systems and tools ● Other (background) material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Any research field ● Clinical research ● Biomedical research ● Cell biology, molecular biology, and biochemistry ● Plant and mycological sciences ● Zoology ● Microbiology ● Marine/water biology ● Ecology ● Environmental sciences ● Life science - other topics 	Data about or from living humans: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Any type of data ● Population level health/or socio-economic data ● Real world or routine health data ● Clinical research data ● Public health emergency data ● Biobank and sample data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Not applicable ● Whole cycle ● Primary data registration ● Preparation and planning for data sharing ● Actions at the end of a study ● Managing data access and requests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Not applicable ● Global ● Continental ● Country groupings ● National 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No specific topic ● Agreements ● Attribution and credit ● COVID-19 ● Data Repositories ● Data sharing committees ● FAIR and FAIRification ● GDPR ● IP-aspects/licences ● Legal basis for data sharing ● Metadata supporting data sharing ● Privacy protection

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social sciences, legal or ethical research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data with images of humans • Omics and related data (from living humans) • Other specific data type <p>Data not derived from living humans:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any type of data • Population level data • Real world • Observational/interventional research • Public health emergency data • Biobank and sample data • Data with images • Omics and related data • Other specific data type 	for data re-use		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research participants involvement
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Table 1: EOSC-LIFE WP4 toolbox: Updated categorisation system
(short version, version 3, final)

Each of the 7 remaining dimensions are listed below and include a brief description at the top of the dimension itself, followed by tag definitions.

3 Definitions

The majority of definitions were taken from the categorisation system, version 2.

3.1 Sensitive data type

According to the definition used for this project, **sensitive data means** Information that is regulated by law due to possible risk for plants, animals, individuals and/or communities and for public and private organisations (2).

- **Personal data**

Personal data include information related to racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership and data concerning the health or sex life of an individual. These data could be identifiable and potentially cause harm through their disclosure.

- **Environmental data**

Environmental data cover environmental risks (nuclear or other sensitive installations, for example) or environmental preservation (habitats, protected fauna or flora, in particular).

- **Proprietary data**

Proprietary data is generated data or documents that can contain technical or other types of information that is controlled by a firm or public institution to safeguard its competitive edge. It could potentially be protected by copyright, patent or trade secret laws. Under this term intellectual property and licences are also covered as well as embargo.

- **DURC data**

Dual Use Research of Concern (DURC) is life sciences research that, based on current understanding, can be reasonably anticipated to provide knowledge, information, products, or technologies that could be directly misapplied to pose a significant threat with broad potential consequences to public health and safety, agricultural crops and other plants, animals, the environment, materiel, or national security (6). In case of environmental data, the term DURC should only be used, if there is an explicit reference to this type of life science research (e.g. in the title, abstract or keywords).

- **Classified information**

Classified Information is material that a government body deems to be sensitive information that must be protected. Access is restricted by law or regulation to particular groups of people with the necessary security clearance and need to know, and mishandling of the material can incur criminal penalties (7). The term classified information has been specified, for example, in EU (8) and US regulations (9).

- **Other sensitive data**

Under “other sensitive data” all resources that do not fall under one of the above categories are allocated.

3.2 Resource type

Resource type is used for a broad categorisation of a resource dependent on the **main subject area(s)** covered by that resource. Examples are ‘Legislation and regulations’, and ‘Support systems and tools’. The categories are purposely broad, to try and ensure all resources can be categorised in this dimension relatively easily.

The expectation is that every resource should be linked to at least one of these tags – in most cases only one. There is no ‘not applicable’ or ‘other’ option, though there is ‘Other background material’.

- **Legislation and regulations**
Includes any legislation and official regulatory documents relevant to data sharing in any domain, (e.g. from national regulatory or data protection bodies), commentaries on and interpretations of those documents, including analysis of the possible impact of legislation / regulations and the perceived need for new or revised legislation / regulations, and accounts and comments on individual judgements (case law).
- **Guidelines, recommendations, and policies**
Includes any statements from organisations (e.g. from research funders, publishers, individual companies, institutions, academic collaborations, and research infrastructures) or from individual researchers / groups of researchers, that propose policies, behaviours, standards, or codes of conduct to be followed on any aspect of data sharing. The policies and principles may be expressed as guidance or in some contexts (e.g. within a particular institution) may be mandated as necessary practice. They may cover all or just specific aspects of data sharing activity. ***In the majority of cases, the resource’s title or sub-title should include one or other of the terms guideline, recommendations, policy or code of conduct.***
- **Descriptions of (best) practice**
Descriptions, comparisons and reviews of concrete instances of data sharing, or of some aspect of data sharing. May include, for example, survey data on the extent of data sharing, descriptions of data sharing initiatives, comparisons of data sharing activity over time or between different research types, and individual case studies and reports. The practices described should be considered ‘best practice’. May focus on the mechanisms of data sharing employed, and / or the scientific impact of the sharing activity.
- **Support systems and tools**
Examples, descriptions and reviews of support systems, infrastructures, tools and services that are designed to directly support data sharing activities. May include for example data repositories, data anonymization tools and algorithms, example SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) and proformas (e.g. Data Use Agreement templates), websites providing advice and suggestions, or detailed instructions or FAQs (Frequently Asked Questions) for specific tools, software or infrastructures. Training systems and material should also be included under this tag.
- **Other (background) material**
Any material that does not fit into the categories listed above but which provides useful background material relevant to data sharing. Examples include position papers from influential groups or organisations, discussions of publication bias in journals, descriptions of IT security measures, or discussions over reproducibility in research.

3.3 Research Field

“Research field” describes the scientific field or fields which are the **source** of the resource and / or the data discussed or described within it. The classification has been kept as simple as possible but tries to reflect the RIs in EOSC-Life. In addition, input from existing classifications has been used (10,

11, 12, 13, 14). The expectation is that every resource should be linked to at least one of these research field tags – in most cases only one. There is a ‘Life sciences – other topics’ option, however, for any fields that seem to have been excluded (the use of which could be periodically reviewed).

- **Clinical research**

Interventional or observational studies of living humans with the explicit intention of answering questions about health, ill-health and its care and treatment. Includes clinical trials, the use of observational studies including epidemiological and population level research, using disease registry and biobank data, using data extracted from routine health care records, and associated imaging, genetic, histological, and biochemical analyses. Includes later stages of translational research.

- **Biomedical research**

Research in anatomy, developmental biology, endocrinology, immunology, neurology, nutrition, parasitology, pathology, pharmacology, physiology, and related disciplines, intended to improve understanding of normal and abnormal functioning in animals, and in particular in humans. May or may not use material taken from living humans. Not intended to directly impact medical or health practice though may suggest (or have been suggested by) related clinical research. May include work on model organisms such as mice. Includes early stages of translational research.

If one resource covers different fields from medical/health research (e.g., clinical research, biomedical research), all applicable tags from the dimension “research fields” should be selected.

- **Cell biology, molecular biology, and biochemistry**

The study of inter- and intra-cellular processes, structural biology, molecular biology, biochemical, genetic, genomic, and other -omic research may be focused on “biomedical research”. In that case “biomedical research” should be documented. In all other cases (other life science areas), the tag “cell biology, molecular biology, and biochemistry” should be chosen.

- **Plant and mycological sciences**

Studies of the classification, form, behaviour, evolution, physiology, genetics, biochemistry, molecular biology, etc., of specific multicellular plants and fungi, including close symbioses such as lichens but excluding marine species and interactions between species. Excludes studies on model organisms intended to explore processes more generally at the intra-cellular level.

- **Zoology**

Studies of the classification, form, behaviour, evolution, physiology, genetics, biochemistry, molecular biology, etc., of specific multicellular animals, excluding marine species and interactions between species. Excludes studies on model organisms intended to explore processes more generally at the intra-cellular level.

- **Microbiology**

Research in bacteriology, virology, and the biology of single celled eukaryotes. Includes the study of microorganisms in health and disease, microbial resistance to therapeutics and the study of microbiomes. Also includes the roles of microorganisms within food and medicine production, and within cycles of nutrients and material in the biosphere.

- **Marine/water biology**
Studies of the ecosystems, interactions between species at individual and population level, interactions with environmental factors, and the impact of humans (including fishing), in or on the edges of the sea and freshwater.
- **Ecology**
Research into ecosystems, interactions between species at individual and population level.
- **Environmental sciences**
Interactions of life with environmental factors, and the impact of humans including agriculture and climate change. Excludes sea or freshwater water-based ecosystems.
- **Life science - other topics**
Topics within the life sciences that do not fit within any of the categories above.
- **Social sciences, legal or ethical research**
Research in anthropology, archaeology, bioethics, communication studies, economics, education, ethics and bioethics, geography, history, law, linguistics, political science, psychology, sociology, and related sub-disciplines.

3.4 Data type

The type of data that is the subject or **focus** of the resource. On the highest level, there will be a discrimination between “data about or from living humans” and “data not derived from living humans”. If the resource is dealing with human data, it has to be assessed, whether the resource is specifically about one (or more) data types or not. This is also done for “data not derived from living humans”. If the resource is not about a specific data type, it may be about “any type of data”, without specifying a specific data type (or equivalently, such data considered as a whole). For selection of specific data type(s), a pre-defined list of data types will be provided. There may be the situation that the resource is about a specific data type, but the data type is not on the pre-specified list. In that case the tag “other specific data type” should be used. For data not derived from living humans a similar list is provided with some exceptions.

The tags should be used to match the focus, or foci, of the resource. For example:

- i) If a resource is concerned only with sharing X-ray images, it should be tagged with ‘Data with images of humans’, and does *not* need to be also tagged with ‘Any type of data about living humans’.
- ii) If a resource is concerned with sharing sensitive human data, in general, legal or without considering any particular subtypes of that data in detail, it should be tagged with ‘Any type of data (about living humans)’.
- iii) If a resource is concerned with sharing sensitive human data and includes in a subsection a particular focus on sharing X-ray images, it should be tagged with *both* ‘Data with images of humans’ *and* ‘Any type of data (about living humans)’.

The expectation is that unless a resource deals with data sharing in general it will have at least one of these tags applied to it.

Data about or from living humans

- **Any type of data (about living humans)**
A resource that describes or discusses the sharing of data obtained from or about humans, in general. It may or may not include a detailed statement of particular data types (if it does that should also be tagged). An example would be a resource about general data protection legislation.
- **Population level health or socio-economic data**
Resources dealing with large datasets relating to defined populations, with usually at least several thousand participants, but often tens or hundreds of thousands, for example derived from epidemiological research or census data. This may include sensitive data, e.g. relating to health status.
- **Real world or routine health data**
Resources focused mainly on sharing EHR (electronic health record), care episode and insurance data, but may also include lifestyle and wearable derived data.
- **Clinical research data**
Resources concerned with sharing data from both interventional and observational clinical studies, based on defined and approved protocols. Also those resources focused on the sharing of datasets relating to populations with specific diseases (registry data).
- **Public health emergency data**
For example data relating to COVID-19 patients, or people with Ebola or SARS. A distinct category of data because regulations concerning the re-use of such data, at least during a defined period, may vary from other health related data, and because specialist infrastructures (e.g. COVID-19 data repositories) often exist.
- **Biobank and sample data**
Sharing data about samples, usually including associated genomic data and / or phenotypic details. “biobank and sample data” often will include associated genomic data and usually also phenotypic data.
- **Data with images of humans**
Concerned with the sharing of any type of image data, including photographs and videos, as well as X-rays, NMR scans, PET scans, ultrasound scans etc.
- **Omic and related data (from living humans)**
Focused on the sharing of gene sequences and gene expression data, histochemistry and metabolomic data from individuals, usually taken in the context of health or genetic or biochemical research. May or may not include phenotypic data points and indirect identifiers.
There may be “omics and related data” with no specific reference to a biobank, which should be documented under this tag.
- **Other specific data type (from living humans)**

If the resource is about a specific data type, but the data type is not listed, this tag should be used.

Data not derived from living humans

- **Any type of data**
A resource that describes or discusses the sharing of data not obtained from humans, in general.
- **Population level health status/asset**
Resources dealing with large datasets relating to defined non-human populations,
- **Real world**
Routinely collected data from non-humans
- **Observational/Interventional research**
Resources concerned with sharing data from both interventional and observational studies, based on defined and approved protocols and dealing with non-human data.
- **Public health emergency data**
For example data relating to COVID-19 disease (e.g., data about virus variants).
- **Biobank and sample data**
Sharing data about samples, usually including associated genomic data and / or phenotypic details. “biobank and sample data” often will include associated genomic data and usually also phenotypic data
- **Data with images**
Concerned with the sharing of any type of image data, including photographs and videos, as well as X-rays, NMR scans, PET scans, ultrasound scans etc.
- **Omics and related data (not from living humans)**
Focused on the sharing of gene sequences and gene expression data, and other -omics data from organisms other than humans.
- **Other or any data type (not from living humans)**
This tag covers all cases of non-human data not falling under the listed data types.

3.5 Stage in the data sharing life cycle

Some resources are concerned with, or fit within, a specific stage in the data sharing ‘life cycle’, for example the preparatory steps required for data sharing as part of study planning, or actions required at study end (such as data de-identification), or mechanisms for dealing with data requests (15, 16). If this is the case, one or more of the tags listed below should be applied. If not, this dimension should be explicitly labelled as ‘Not applicable’. Resources that are explicitly focused on the whole of the data sharing cycle should be tagged with ‘Whole cycle’. Resources that cover more than one specific stage may have multiple tags assigned to them.

- **Whole cycle**

Used for resources that **explicitly** cover the whole of the data sharing process or life cycle. General resources on data sharing that do not explicitly consider the sequence or timing of events and actions should not be tagged in this way. The tag is only for resources that take or include a sequential approach to describing the whole data sharing activity.

If this more generic tag does not apply but one or more specific stages in the data sharing life cycle are considered in the resource, the stage(s) should be taken from the following list:

- **Primary data registration**
- **Preparation and planning for data**
For resources that consider part or all of the preparations required to share data, either in general or at the beginning of a specific research project. This can include training of staff, specifying relevant SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures), specifying the data sharing plans in a DMP (Data Management Plan) including the likely data and documents to be shared and when, creating public statements about data sharing (e.g. in a trial registry), designing appropriate consent forms, using standards for data structures, and estimating resources required and costs.
- **Actions at the end of a study**
For resources that consider part or all of the preparations required to put data sharing into action at the end of a study, including preparation of data by de-identification, preparing appropriate metadata, obtaining advice on the legal basis for data sharing, transfer of data objects to a repository and the use of data transfer agreements, specifying access conditions etc.
- **Managing data access and requests for data re-use**
Resources that consider all or part of the processes involved in managing data access once data is ready for sharing, including promoting discovery of materials, and negotiating and using Data Use Agreements (Data Access Agreements), using Data Access Committees, etc. This tag also covers organisation of data sharing.
- **Not applicable**
This tag should be used if a stage (or stages) in the data sharing life cycle cannot be allocated to a resource. If the full data sharing life cycle is covered, the tag “whole cycle” should be used.

3.6 Geographical scope

This tag should indicate, when one exists, the named geographical scope of the resource. The geographic origin of the resource’s authors or its source organisation is not important – it is the **scope of the resource** itself that is relevant. Geographic scopes exist at different scales: global, regional, and national. A tag should only be applied when the geographic scope is obvious or explicit, e.g. legislation or regulations that apply only to one country, or a survey of data sharing within a single continent or region. Names of countries and other geographic entities are taken from standard lists (17). Resources without a clear geographical scope should have this tag marked as not applicable.

- **Not applicable**
For resources with no explicit reference to a geographical scope.

If there is an explicit reference to a geographical scope (and “not applicable” does not apply), the scope should be specified using the list below:

- **Global**
A resource that has an explicitly global scope (in intent if not always in reality), such as ICH GCP (International Conference on Harmonisation - Good Clinical Practice) or a WHO (World Health Organisation) document and discussions around it.
- **Continental**
For resources with a continental scope. Should be one of Africa, Asia, Europe, North-America, South-America (excluding Central America and the Caribbean), or Oceania
- **Country groupings**
For a resource that is focused on a named region or other grouping of countries, or a widely recognised area e.g. ‘Middle East’, ‘Caribbean’, ‘Sub-Saharan Africa’, ‘Nordic countries’, ‘Arctic region’. An important grouping for many resources is likely to be the EU (European Union). A further significant grouping may be LMIC (Low and middle income countries). A list needs to be created of these groupings. A standard list is available from the UN (United Nations), but experience in using the system may amend this.
- **National**
When the scope is purely national, the country name. The name should be taken from the standardised ISO (International Standardization Organization) list (<https://unstats.un.org/unsd/methodology/m49/>, (17)), but should focus on countries likely to be important. The suggestion is all countries in Europe, plus countries elsewhere with a population over a certain size, e.g. 5 million.

3.7 Specific topics

These are a selection of ‘keywords’ that relate to important topics within data sharing, and which are not covered elsewhere in the tagging scheme. They tend to be discrete topics that are significant, newsworthy, or troublesome, and thus the subject of resources. Some tags cover several related or constituent terms to reduce observer disagreement between experts. In such cases searching on one of the related terms will identify all resources with the ‘parent’ tag. In the list below some initial suggestions for matching search terms are made but these lists will need discussion and in many cases expanding. A resource may have any number of specific topic keywords attached, but there is no requirement for such tags to be used. They are simply added if and when appropriate.

- **Agreements**
Includes as matching search terms Data Use (or Access) Agreements, Data (or Material) Transfer Agreement, Data Storage Agreements and their abbreviations.
- **Attribution and credit**
Includes as matching search terms Attribution, Citations, Data authorship, Incentives, Credit, (all for data sharing).

- **COVID-19**
Includes as matching terms COVID (coronavirus disease), SARS-2 (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus-2), Coronavirus.
- **Data Repositories**
Includes as matching terms Repository, Repositories, Long-term Data Storage.
- **Data sharing committees**
Includes as matching terms Data Access Committee.
- **FAIR and FAIRification**
In 2016, the ‘FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship’ were published in *Scientific Data*. The authors intended to provide guidelines to improve the **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**euse of digital assets. The principles emphasise machine-actionability (i.e., the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume, complexity, and creation speed of data. A practical “how to” guidance to go FAIR can be found in the Three-point FAIRification Framework (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>). .
- **GDPR**
General Data Protection Regulation
- **IP-aspects/licences**
Include as matching terms IP (Intellectual property), Licences, Creative Commons
- **Legal basis for data sharing**
Includes as matching terms Informed consent, Broad consent, Alternatives to consent, Public interest, Legitimate interest.
- **Metadata supporting data sharing**
Includes as matching terms Metadata, Metadata standards, Descriptive metadata.
- **Privacy protection**
Includes as matching terms Anonymisation, Pseudonymisation, De-identification
- **Research participants involvement**
Includes as matching terms Participants, Patient Group, Community involvement

3.8 Other metadata

Note that there are other metadata items that can and should be attached to resources for informational purposes, which could also be potentially used within searches, but which are not part of the tagging process. These include resource class (text, video, audio, software, etc.) or type (webinar, FAQ list, published paper, legislation, web page, etc.), authors (names of both people and organisations), file type and size, and year of publication.

4 Next steps

This version was approved by the toolbox group of EOSC-Life WP4 on 22 October 2021. As a next step, the 110 resources will be re-tagged with version 3. The newly tagged resources will constitute the basic content for the demonstrator of the toolbox.

3 References

1. Boiten, Jan-Willem; Ohmann, Christian; Adeniran, Ayodeji; Canham, Steve; Cano Abadia, Monica; Chassang, Gauthier; Chiusano, Maria Luisa; David, Romain; Fratelli, Maddalena; Gribbon, Phil; Holub, Petr; Ludwig, Rebecca; Mayrhofer, Michaela Th.; Matei, Mihaela; Merchant, Arshiya; Panagiotopoulou, Maria; Pireddu, Luca; Sanchez Pla, Alex; Schlünder, Irene; George Tsamis; Wagener, Harald. (2021, January 31). EOSC-LIFE WP4 TOOLBOX: Toolbox for sharing of sensitive data - a concept description. Zenodo.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4483694>
2. David, Romain, Mabile, Laurence, Specht, Alison, Stryeck, Sarah, Thomsen, Mogens, Yahia, Mohamed, Jonquet, Clement, Dollé, Laurent, Jacob, Daniel, Bailo, Daniele, Bravo, Helena, Gachet, Sophie, Gunderman, Hannah, Hollebecq, Jean-Eudes, Ioannidis, Vassilios, Le Bras, Yvan, Lerigoleur, Emilie, Cambon-Thomsen, Anne, & SHARC Community. (2020). Templates for FAIRness evaluation criteria - RDA-SHARC ig (1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3922069>
3. Ohmann, Christian; Canham, Steve; Boiten, Jan-Willem; Cano Abadía, Mónica; Chassang, Gautier; Chiusano, Marie Luisa; David, Romain; Mayrhofer, Michaela Th.; Pireddu, Luca. (2020, December 8). EOSC-Life WP4 Toolbox: Categorisation system for resources to be referenced in the toolbox for sharing of sensitive data (Version 1). Zenodo.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4311094>
4. Ohmann, Christian (ECRIN, pilot study coordinator); David, Romain (ERINHA); Cano Abadia, Monica (BBMRI); Biatrix, Florence (EATRIS); Boiten, Jan-Willem (EATRIS/Lygature); Canham, Steve (ECRIN); Chiusano, Maria Luisa (EMBRC), Dastru, Walter (Euro-Biolmaging; Laroquette, Arnaud (EMBRC), Longo, Dario (Euro-Biolmaging), Mayrhofer, Michaela Th. (BBMRI); Panagiotopoulou, Maria (ECRIN); Richard, Audrey (ERINHA); Verde, Pablo (2021). Pilot study on the intercalibration of a categorisation system for FAIRer digital objects related to sensitive data in the life-sciences. Submitted to Data Intelligence Journal
5. Ohmann, Christian (ECRIN, pilot study coordinator); Cano Abadia, Monica (BBMRI), Biatrix, Florence (EATRIS); Boiten, Jan-Willem (EATRIS/Lygature); Canham, Steve (ECRIN); Chiusano, Maria Luisa (EMBRC); Dastru, Walter (Euro-Biolmaging); David, Romain (ERINHA); Laroquette, Arnaud (EMBRC); Longo, Dario (Euro-Biolmaging); Mayrhofer, Michaela Th. (BBMRI); Panagiotopoulou, Maria (ECRIN); Richard Audrey (ERINHA) (2021). The EOSC-Life WP4 toolbox: Update of the categorisation system. Zenodo.
<https://zenodo.org/record/5506762#.YWW6-9pBw2w>
6. NIH, Office of Science Policy: Dual Use Research of Concern (assessed 14.09.2021)
<https://osp.od.nih.gov/biotechnology/dual-use-research-of-concern/>

7. Wikipedia: Classified information (assessed 14.09.2021).
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Classified_information
8. Official Journal of the European Union: COUNCIL DECISION of 23 September 2013 on the security rules for protecting EU classified information
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013D0488&from=EN>
9. NIST. InformationTechnology Laboratory. Computer Security Resource Center. Glossary: Classified information
https://csrc.nist.gov/glossary/term/classified_information
10. OECD Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development.
<https://www.oecd.org/publications/frascati-manual-2015-9789264239012-en.htm>
11. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge Author Services: Areas of Study (assessed 14.09.2021). <https://www.cambridge.org/academic/author-services/areas-of-study/>
12. The World University Rankings: Subject Ranking 2015-2016: life sciences top 100.
https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/2016/subject-ranking/life-sciences-0#!/page/0/length/25/sort_by/rank/sort_order/asc/cols/stats
13. Clarivate Analytics. Web of Science Core Collection Help: Research Areas (Categories/classification).
https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/hp_research_areas_easca.html
14. Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC) (2008 edition): National Health and Medical Research Council Fields of Research (FOR).
<https://www.abs.gov.au/Ausstats/abs@.nsf/Latestproducts/4AE1B46AE2048A28CA25741800044242?opendocument>
15. UK Data Archive: [Data life cycle & data management planning 2013](#).
<https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/media/187718/dmplanningdm24apr2013.pdf>
16. Ohmann, Christian; Canham, Steve; Banzi, Rita; Kuchinke, Wolfgang; Battaglia, Serena. Classification of processes involved in sharing individual participant data from clinical trials [version 2; peer review: 3 approved]. *F1000Research* 2018, 7:138
<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.13789.2>
17. United Nations: Standard country or area codes for statistical use (M49) (assessed 14.09.2021).
<https://unstats.un.org/unsd/methodology/m49/>